

Cause and Effect Relationship of Mortgage Loans and Indian Economy

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the cause-and-effect relationship between mortgage lending and macroeconomic indicators in India, addressing the limited use of advanced econometric methods and the lack of country-specific focus in existing literature. Using quarterly data from FY 2010–11 to 2024–25 sourced from the Reserve Bank of India, the study analyzes the interactions between mortgage-related variables—such as disbursements, outstanding loans, NPAs, and interest rates—and key economic indicators like GDP growth, inflation, unemployment, and house prices. Employing descriptive statistics, trend analysis, and correlation matrices, the research further applies time-series techniques including the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test, Johansen cointegration, Granger causality, Vector Autoregression (VAR), and Impulse Response Functions to capture both short-run dynamics and long-term equilibrium relationships. Findings confirm that while most variables are non-stationary individually, they are cointegrated, indicating strong long-term linkages. GDP significantly influences mortgage disbursements and inflation, while interest rate fluctuations impact credit activity and financial stress. The bidirectional dynamics identified suggest that mortgage lending is both a consequence and a driver of economic performance. These insights emphasize the need for integrated policy approaches aligning housing finance, monetary tools, and regulatory oversight to promote economic resilience and sustainable growth.

Introduction

Mortgage loans play a vital role in modern financial systems by enabling home ownership, stimulating demand in real estate and construction sectors, and influencing broader economic activity through consumption and investment channels (Warnock & Warnock, 2008). In India, the mortgage market has expanded significantly over the past two decades, driven by rapid urbanization, a growing middle class, and supportive policy interventions such as the Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana (Gopalan & Venkataraman, 2015). This growth has been further accelerated by financial sector reforms and the emergence of housing finance companies, supported by regulatory frameworks established by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI, 2021).

The macroeconomic implications of mortgage lending are substantial. Rising mortgage credit contributes to GDP growth, job creation, and asset formation, while also serving as a key transmission channel for monetary policy (Das, 2018). However, the relationship between mortgage lending and economic performance is complex. While credit growth can boost development, it also raises concerns about financial stability, including household overleveraging, asset price inflation, and interest rate sensitivity (Debelle, 2004).

In addition, factors such as income inequality, regional disparities, the increasing role of fintech in credit delivery, and evolving regulatory norms have added layers of complexity to this relationship (Fuster et al., 2019; Singh & Pattanaik, 2020). These dynamics highlight the need for a deeper, data-driven understanding of how mortgage lending interacts with broader macroeconomic indicators in India. This study seeks to address this gap by analyzing historical mortgage and economic data, identifying causal linkages, and assessing the long-run equilibrium between mortgage-related variables and macroeconomic performance.

Literature Review

1. Role of Financial Technology in Mortgage Lending

Fuster et al. (2019) conducted a comparative study on fintech versus traditional mortgage lenders using a dataset from the U.S. mortgage market. They applied regression models and matched samples to control for borrower characteristics and loan terms. Key variables included loan approval time, borrower credit score, default rates, and interest rates. Their analysis revealed that fintech lenders processed mortgages more quickly—up to 20% faster—without increasing default risk. Additionally, fintech lenders offered more consistent pricing and served a broader range of borrowers, including those in low-income and minority groups. These findings demonstrate that technology not only improves efficiency and borrower experience but also maintains, and in some cases enhances, loan performance and credit access.

2. Mortgage Debt and Consumption During the Great Recession

Kaplan, Mitman, and Violante (2020) employed a structural heterogeneous-agent model to examine how mortgage debt influenced consumption during the U.S. Great Recession. The study incorporated variables such as housing liquidity, household debt levels, consumption spending, and home prices. Their simulation-based approach highlighted that in regions with high mortgage leverage and illiquid housing markets, declines in home prices caused disproportionately large drops in consumption. This was especially true for households with limited access to liquid assets. The research reinforced the notion that mortgage design and housing market liquidity play vital roles in macroeconomic resilience and can amplify or mitigate the effects of economic downturns.

3. Borrower Profile in the Housing Boom

Adelino, Schoar, and Severino (2016) analyzed loan-level data from mortgage originations in the early 2000s to investigate the income profile of borrowers during the U.S. housing boom. Using statistical analysis of variables such as income levels, loan amounts, and home purchase patterns, the authors found that middle- and high-income borrowers—not just low-income ones—were primarily responsible for the surge in mortgage debt. Contrary to the common narrative, their results suggest that credit expansion was broad-based and not limited to subprime markets. This finding challenges earlier research by Mian and Sufi (2009) and carries implications for macroprudential policy, which must consider all income groups when assessing systemic risk from housing bubbles.

4. Optimal Mortgage Contract Design

Piskorski and Tchistyi (2010) developed a continuous-time general equilibrium model to evaluate the welfare implications of different mortgage structures, such as fixed-rate and adjustable-rate mortgages. The key variables in their analysis included interest rate volatility, borrower income shocks, foreclosure rates, and default penalties. Their theoretical model showed that contracts offering flexibility—particularly those allowing for payment adjustments based on income or market conditions—can reduce foreclosure rates and improve borrower welfare. The study concluded that optimal mortgage design can serve as a tool to improve economic stability, and it supports prior findings from Brueckner (2000) and Campbell and Cocco (2003) regarding the importance of risk-sharing in financial products.

5. Housing Financialization and Supply Constraints

Rognlie (2022) conducted a macroeconomic analysis using panel data and regression techniques to explore how financialization—specifically the rise in mortgage credit—affects housing supply and capital formation. The study focused on variables such as mortgage debt levels, residential investment, housing starts, and urban housing prices. Contrary to traditional assumptions, the analysis found that increased mortgage credit often led to underinvestment in new housing stock, particularly in high-demand urban areas. Instead of boosting supply, the capital was funneled into existing property markets, inflating prices. This research adds to the literature on urban housing dynamics by showing that unchecked mortgage expansion can distort investment priorities and hinder affordable housing development.

6. Real Estate Investment in the Post-Pandemic Era

In this study, the researchers analyzed shifts in real estate investment strategies following the COVID-19 pandemic, using qualitative surveys and secondary data from global property markets. The variables included investment preferences, ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) considerations, digital infrastructure readiness, and tenant health metrics. The methodology involved thematic analysis and comparative case studies of property portfolios before and after the pandemic. The findings revealed a clear transition from traditional investment priorities—like location and expected return—to more adaptive criteria that emphasize resilience, sustainability, and health-related infrastructure. Investors increasingly valued properties with features like air purification, flexible layouts, and smart technologies. The study aligns with evolving perspectives on real estate resilience outlined by Geltner et al. (2007) and Ling and Naranjo (2021), highlighting the pandemic's transformative impact on asset allocation.

7. Impact of Platforms on Urban Real Estate

Fields, Bissell, and Macrorie (2021) used a critical urban theory framework combined with ethnographic and spatial analysis methods to assess how digital platforms—such as Airbnb and Opendoor—are reshaping urban real estate markets. Variables studied included rental prices, landlord behavior, housing turnover rates, and platform usage data. The authors demonstrated that digital platforms facilitate rent extraction, alter traditional landlord-tenant dynamics, and contribute to increased housing market volatility. Their findings also revealed patterns of gentrification and displacement linked to short-term rental platforms. The research situates itself within broader discussions of platform capitalism (Srnicek, 2017) and financialized housing systems (Aalbers, 2016), calling attention to how technology can reinforce existing housing inequalities and transform urban governance structures.

8. Credit Supply and Speculation

Kermani (2022) conducted a quantitative study using loan-level mortgage data and housing transaction records to differentiate between speculative and non-speculative homebuyers. Employing regression analysis and credit expansion models, the study focused on variables such as loan-to-value ratios, borrower investment intent, home price appreciation, and credit availability. The results showed that periods of relaxed lending standards disproportionately fueled purchases by speculative investors, who contributed to housing price inflation and increased market risk. These speculative activities were more pronounced in markets with rapid credit growth. The research builds on the frameworks established by Mian and Sufi (2009, 2014) and Glaeser et al. (2008), warning that excessive credit supply without regulatory checks can lead to systemic housing market instability.

9. Structuring Mortgages for Macroeconomic Stability

Campbell, Clara, and Cocco (2020) developed a heterogeneous-agent model to evaluate the macroeconomic effects of different mortgage structures under economic stress. Their methodology included simulations using consumption and income data, mortgage contract terms, and macroeconomic shock scenarios. Key variables included borrower income volatility, refinancing rates, default probabilities, and consumption smoothing mechanisms. The study found that mortgage designs incorporating built-in safeguards—like automatic refinancing options or payment relief clauses—helped stabilize household consumption and reduced default risk during downturns. These contracts promoted financial resilience and could buffer the economy during recessions. Their conclusions reinforce earlier findings by Campbell and Cocco (2003) and Kaplan et al. (2020), suggesting that thoughtful mortgage structuring is vital for economic stability.

10. Monetary Policy and the Housing Boom

Justiniano, Primiceri, and Tambalotti (2019) used a Dynamic Stochastic General Equilibrium (DSGE) model to analyze the drivers behind the 2000s U.S. housing boom. The model incorporated variables such as loan-to-value ratios, interest rates, credit supply indicators, and household borrowing behavior. Contrary to theories emphasizing monetary policy (e.g., Taylor, 2007), their results pointed to credit supply expansion and increasing leverage as primary drivers of the housing bubble, rather than low interest rates alone. The research emphasized the role of financial innovation and relaxed lending conditions in fueling unsustainable housing price growth. Their findings shift the policy focus from interest rate manipulation to better regulation of credit markets as a means of preventing future bubbles.

11. Bank Performance and Economic Growth in India

Ray and Das (2014) applied panel cointegration and causality tests using time-series data from Indian commercial banks to explore the long-term relationship between banking performance and GDP growth. The study used variables such as credit expansion, return on assets, non-performing assets (NPAs), capital adequacy, and GDP growth rates. Their econometric methodology allowed them to assess both short-run dynamics and long-run equilibrium relationships. The results showed that improved bank performance, especially in terms of profitability and asset quality, positively influenced economic growth in India. The study validated the finance-growth nexus outlined by King and Levine (1993), emphasizing that a robust banking sector is critical for channeling funds into productive investment and sustaining macroeconomic development.

12. Credit Risk Management and NPAs in India

Using a case study approach supported by data from Indian public and private sector banks, this research examined how poor credit risk management (CRM) practices contribute to rising levels of non-performing assets (NPAs). Key variables included credit appraisal procedures, monitoring mechanisms, loan default rates, and provisioning norms. Through qualitative analysis and statistical reviews, the study concluded that lax credit appraisal systems, over-reliance on collateral, and ineffective borrower monitoring were key contributors to the NPA crisis in India. Supported by earlier studies such as Rajan and Dhal (2003), the paper also referenced Basel Committee guidelines, highlighting the need for risk-sensitive CRM frameworks to enhance lending quality and financial stability.

13. Critical Housing Studies on Platform Real Estate

Fields (2022) conducted a qualitative and interdisciplinary review advocating for a critical housing studies agenda focused on digital platforms and their impact on housing access and governance. The study employed discourse analysis, policy review, and urban ethnography to examine variables such as housing affordability, platform regulation, data transparency, and tenant rights. The findings emphasized that the growth of real estate platforms has intensified housing commodification, reduced affordability, and reshaped urban governance. The paper calls for a new research direction that integrates sociology, economics, and urban planning to address the inequalities emerging from tech-driven housing markets, reinforcing themes from earlier work by Aalbers (2016) and Srnicek (2017).

14. Framing the Housing Affordability Crisis

Gabriel et al. (2021) synthesized existing quantitative and qualitative literature to critique conventional measures of housing affordability, such as the 30% income rule. Variables analyzed included income levels, rent burden, spatial segregation, housing supply elasticity, and labor precarity. The methodology involved meta-analysis and policy framework evaluation. The authors argued that simplistic affordability ratios fail to capture the multifaceted nature of housing stress, particularly for low-income groups and precarious workers. Their findings emphasized the importance of integrating broader socioeconomic factors—like income inequality and urban displacement—into housing policy. Referencing foundational works like Stone (2006), the study advocated for comprehensive and equity-driven policy reform.

15. Low-Cost Housing Through Earthen Materials

Agarwal and Charania (2015) carried out a field-based study combining experimental construction techniques and architectural analysis to evaluate the use of earthen materials in rural Indian housing. The research involved testing variables like material cost, thermal performance, structural durability, and environmental impact. Their findings highlighted that earthen construction is not only cost-effective and sustainable but also culturally appropriate and scalable for low-income housing. By comparing traditional methods with modern construction standards, the authors argued for integrating indigenous knowledge into state housing policies. Their work resonates with earlier research by Houben and Guillaud (1994) and Bhatt (2013), suggesting that localized, eco-friendly materials can address rural housing challenges affordably.

16. Profitability Comparison Across Construction Sectors

Gupta and Yadav (2021) performed a comparative financial analysis across three major construction sectors in India—real estate, infrastructure, and industrial construction—using secondary data from financial statements. The study utilized variables such as net profit margin, return on equity (ROE), earnings per share (EPS), and debt-to-equity ratio over a five-year period. Through ratio analysis and ANOVA testing, the authors found that real estate firms exhibited higher profitability volatility due to market sensitivity and speculative demand, while infrastructure firms demonstrated more stable returns owing to long project cycles and steady government contracts. Their findings suggest the importance of sectoral differentiation when assessing investment risks and returns in construction.

17. Urban Land Expansion and Economic Growth

Seto, Güneralp, and Hutya (2012) employed remote sensing and spatial econometric techniques to analyze satellite data from over 300 cities globally, including rapidly urbanizing Indian cities, to examine patterns of urban land expansion. Key variables included population growth, GDP per capita, urban footprint change, and environmental indicators like vegetation loss. The study found that economic and population growth are primary drivers of urban sprawl, but rapid, unplanned expansion often leads to loss of green cover and inefficient land use. The research highlighted the need for integrated urban planning that balances economic development with ecological sustainability, reinforcing concerns raised by the IPCC on urban climate risks.

18. Retail Real Estate Transformations Post-COVID

Worzala & Sirmans (2021) and Donthu & Gustafsson (2020) used survey-based methods and market trend analysis to investigate how the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted retail real estate. Variables included retail foot traffic, online sales growth, consumer sentiment, and rent prices. The studies employed both qualitative thematic analysis and quantitative forecasting to determine emerging trends. They found that the pandemic accelerated the decline of traditional brick-and-mortar retail, increased demand for flexible leasing, and pushed developers toward mixed-use, experiential, and digitally integrated spaces. The research emphasized the necessity for retail landlords to innovate and adapt to evolving consumer behaviors and technological integration.

19. Mergers and Acquisitions in Real Estate

Sharma and Ahuja (2020) conducted an event study and financial ratio analysis to evaluate the impact of mergers and acquisitions (M&A) in India's construction and real estate sector. The study examined pre- and post-merger financial performance using variables such as stock price changes, revenue growth, cost efficiency, and return on assets. Their findings were mixed—while some mergers led to enhanced market share and operational synergy, others failed due to integration issues, poor strategic alignment, and regulatory bottlenecks. The research aligns with global studies by Ghosh (2001) and Kumar (2009), emphasizing that M&A success is contingent on execution and market conditions.

20. Dividend Policy Determinants in Real Estate Firms

Singh and Kaur (2020) utilized panel regression models to analyze the determinants of dividend policies among Indian real estate firms. The study used financial data across multiple years, evaluating variables such as profitability (measured through net income and ROE), liquidity (current ratio), firm size, leverage, and institutional ownership. The results indicated that firms with higher profitability and liquidity were more likely to pay dividends, whereas high leverage and significant institutional ownership negatively influenced dividend payouts. The findings support agency theory and signaling theory, illustrating how financial health and ownership structures shape dividend strategies in capital-intensive sectors like real estate.

21. Housing Policy Impact on Real Estate Markets

Kamal and Alam (2022) performed a systematic literature review of over 100 empirical studies to evaluate the effectiveness of various housing policies on real estate market outcomes across different countries, with special emphasis on emerging economies like India. Variables reviewed included housing supply elasticity, policy instruments (subsidies, rent controls), housing affordability metrics, and institutional governance indicators. Their meta-synthesis revealed that policy success heavily depends on local context, enforcement capacity, and alignment with broader socio-economic goals. They emphasized that one-size-fits-all approaches often fail, advocating for decentralized, inclusive policymaking that addresses both affordability and market stability.

Research Gap

- Limited country-specific focus on India: Most studies examining mortgage loans and economic growth are centered on developed countries or broader emerging markets, with insufficient empirical research focusing solely on India's unique economic, demographic, and regulatory context.
- Insufficient use of advanced statistical techniques in the Indian context: While global literature employs sophisticated econometric tools such as VAR, GMM, and cointegration models, Indian studies often rely on basic methods, limiting the robustness and depth of causal analysis.
- Neglect of bidirectional relationship: Existing research frequently examines only one direction of the relationship—either mortgage lending's effect on growth or vice versa—without exploring their potential dynamic and bidirectional interactions in the Indian scenario.

- Lack of integration between mortgage lending and macro variables: Many Indian studies analyze housing finance in isolation, with limited integration of macroeconomic indicators like inflation, GDP, interest rates, or unemployment to assess the broader economic implications.
- Scarcity of longitudinal and post-crisis data: Indian research often overlooks long-term or post-2008 financial crisis data, missing insights into the resilience and behavior of mortgage markets during periods of economic stress or policy shifts.
- Limited exploration of institutional and policy influences: Despite the major role of regulatory bodies like RBI and NHB and government schemes such as PMAY, there is inadequate analysis of how these institutions and policies impact mortgage lending patterns and economic outcomes.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To examine the historical trends and growth patterns of mortgage lending in India over the past 15 years, focusing on key indicators such as outstanding housing credit, interest rates, and new disbursements.
2. To evaluate the relationship between mortgage loan expansion and macroeconomic indicators including GDP growth, inflation, unemployment, and the housing price index within the Indian economy.
3. To identify potential financial risks associated with rapid growth in the mortgage sector, particularly the rise in non-performing assets (NPAs) and volatility in housing markets.
4. To assess the influence of financial technology (fintech) advancements and policy initiatives on mortgage loan accessibility, credit performance, and their broader economic implications.
5. To establish empirical associations between mortgage-related variables and the performance of the Indian economy through descriptive, trend, and correlation analysis, forming a foundation for future causal investigation.

Research Methodology:

This study adopts a quantitative research approach to analyze the relationship between mortgage lending and key macroeconomic indicators in India. Quarterly data from FY 2010-11 to 2024-25 (60 observations) has been

Sourced primarily from the Reserve Bank of India (RBI).

The variables are categorized as follows:

- Dependent Variables: GDP growth rate, inflation rate (CPI/WPI), unemployment rate, housing price index
- Independent Variables: Outstanding mortgage loans, mortgage interest rates, new mortgage disbursements, NPAs in the housing sector
- Control Variables: Repo rate

Data analysis is conducted using SPSS, employing descriptive statistics, trend analysis, and correlation analysis to examine the impact of mortgage-related factors on economic performance. To understand long term and short term relationship between mortgage variables and macroeconomic indicators analysis is extended to VAR, johansen cointegration test, causality test, impulse response function. This methodology ensures a

Structured, data-driven understanding of housing finance within the broader Indian economic context.

Hypotheses of the Study:

H₀: There is no significant correlation between mortgage-related variables (such as mortgage loan growth, NPAs, interest rates, etc.) and key economic indicators (such as GDP, inflation,

housing prices, etc.) in India over the past 15 years.

H₁: There is a significant correlation between mortgage-related variables (such as mortgage loan growth, NPAs, interest rates, etc.) and key economic indicators (such as GDP, inflation, housing prices, etc.) in India over the past 15 years.

Descriptive Statistics:

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Std. Error (Skewness)	Kurtosis	Std. Error (Kurtosis)
GDP Growth Rate (Annual %)	15	2.535	10.620	6.995389	2.022077	-0.566	0.580	0.832	1.121
CPI Inflation (Annual % Change)	15	3.133	10.867	6.384444	2.488413	0.730	0.580	-0.729	1.121
WPI Inflation (Annual % Change)	15	4.167	9.696	6.689917	1.588208	0.078	0.580	-0.691	1.121
Unemployment Rate (Urban, Age 15+)	15	4.167	9.696	6.689917	1.588208	0.078	0.580	-0.691	1.121
All-India House Price Index (Base: 2010–11 = 100)	15	4.256	10.086	6.588093	1.778727	0.497	0.580	-0.595	1.121
Outstanding Housing Loans (₹ Crore)	15	112000.0	680750.0	325982.470	183327.1290	0.875	0.580	-0.046	1.121
Mortgage Loan Interest Rates (2015–2024)	15	56005.0431	340377.8806	162994.527380	91663.1867	0.875	0.580	-0.046	1.121
New Mortgage Disbursements (2015–2024)	15	27375	99375	57658.330	21777.716	0.672	0.580	-0.472	1.121
NPAs in Housing Sector (2015–2024)	15	0.625	1.950	1.158333	0.362120	0.453	0.580	0.347	1.121
Repo Rate	15	0.040	0.0825	0.063867	0.012373	-0.261	0.580	-0.484	1.121

The descriptive analysis reveals significant insights into the evolution of mortgage lending in India over the past 15 years. Outstanding housing loans have shown a remarkable increase, with values ranging from ₹1,12,000 crore to ₹6,80,750 crore and a high mean of ₹3,25,982 crore, indicating robust growth in mortgage credit. This trend is further supported by substantial new mortgage disbursements, averaging ₹57,658 crore, which reflects a consistent expansion in housing finance. The variability in mortgage loan interest rates, which range widely and show high standard deviation, suggests dynamic lending conditions, likely shaped by shifts in monetary policy, market demand, and technological advancements. The positive skewness observed in both outstanding loans and disbursements implies occasional years of elevated activity, potentially driven by regulatory changes or surges in housing demand.

In examining financial stability, the data on non-performing assets (NPAs) in the housing sector indicates relatively low average levels, but the presence of moderate skewness suggests intermittent stress in the system, possibly due to overleveraging or macroeconomic shocks. The All-India House Price Index shows a stable upward trend with a mean of 6.59, reflecting a relatively balanced housing market without extreme volatility. These indicators collectively point toward a maturing mortgage sector that has grown in scale while facing occasional risk episodes.

The shifts observed in disbursements, loan volumes, and interest rates over the years also hint at the influence of financial innovation and regulatory developments. While not statistically isolated in this analysis, such changes likely reflect increased mortgage accessibility facilitated by digital platforms, policy incentives, and structural reforms aimed at boosting housing finance. Altogether, the descriptive statistics underscore a decade and a half of expanding mortgage activity, evolving market dynamics, and measured exposure to systemic risks in India's housing finance landscape.

Trend analysis:

The analysis of the Indian mortgage and housing sector from 2010–11 to 2024–25 reveals significant economic transitions influenced by both macroeconomic indicators and sector-specific dynamics. The first graph, capturing variables like GDP growth, inflation rates (CPI and WPI), unemployment, NPAs in housing, repo rates, and mortgage rates, highlights a period of relative stability until the economic shock of 2020–21. During that year, the GDP growth rate plummeted, unemployment peaked, and NPAs in housing spiked—clearly reflecting the pandemic's adverse impact. However, this disruption was followed by a sharp economic rebound in 2021–22, evident through a strong GDP recovery and declining NPAs and unemployment rates. Notably, both repo and mortgage rates experienced a consistent decline through the period, particularly after 2015, indicating an accommodative monetary policy that likely supported borrowing and housing investments.

This supportive credit environment is reflected in the second graph, which shows a steady rise in new mortgage disbursements and a significant surge in outstanding housing loans. From ₹1.1 lakh crores in 2010–11, outstanding loans have climbed to nearly ₹7 lakh crores by 2023–24, with a particularly sharp acceleration post-2020. Despite a brief dip in new disbursements during the pandemic, the recovery was robust, indicating renewed confidence in the housing market and improved financial conditions for borrowers.

Complementing these trends, the third graph—depicting the House Price Index—shows a consistent appreciation in residential property values, rising from a base of 100 in 2010–11 to over 320 in 2023–24. This threefold increase underscores strong demand and perceived investment value in real estate, although a minor correction is seen in 2024–25, possibly signaling market stabilization or the effect of regulatory adjustments.

Correlation:

Variables	HPI	GDP Growth	CPI Inflation	WPI Inflation	Outstanding Loans	Interest Rates	New Disbursements	NPAs	Unemployment
All-India House Price Index (HPI)	1	0.361	0.925	0.981	-0.425	0.487	-0.382	0.736	0.249
GDP Growth Rate	0.361	1	-0.019	0.534	0.057	0.023	0.046	0.417	-0.623
CPI Inflation	0.925	-0.019	1	0.835	-0.479	0.513	-0.428	0.620	0.520
WPI Inflation	0.981	0.534	0.835	1	-0.374	0.446	-0.337	0.753	0.097
Outstanding Housing Loans	-0.425	0.057	-0.479	-0.374	1	-0.869	0.964	-0.353	-0.351
Mortgage Loan Interest Rates	0.487	0.023	0.513	0.446	-0.869	1	-0.907	0.679	0.311
New Mortgage Disbursements	-0.382	0.046	-0.428	-0.337	0.964	-0.907	1	-0.405	-0.365
NPAs in Housing Sector	0.736	0.417	0.620	0.753	-0.353	0.679	-0.405	1	0.025
Unemployment Rate (Urban)	0.249	-0.623	0.520	0.097	-0.351	0.311	-0.365	0.025	1

The correlation analysis of various macroeconomic indicators and housing sector variables reveals several insightful patterns. The All-India House Price Index (HPI) exhibits a very strong positive correlation with both Wholesale Price Index (WPI) Inflation and Consumer Price Index (CPI) Inflation,

suggesting that as inflation rises, housing prices tend to increase. This is indicative of a cost-push effect where rising input costs in construction contribute to higher property prices. Additionally, HPI also shows a moderately strong correlation with Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) in the housing sector, which may imply that higher house prices can potentially lead to affordability issues and loan defaults. Interestingly, HPI has only a weak negative correlation with Outstanding Housing Loans and New Mortgage Disbursements, indicating that price appreciation in housing may not be heavily credit-driven.

The GDP growth rate, while showing a moderate positive correlation with WPI inflation, has relatively weak correlations with most housing variables. However, it has a notable negative correlation with the unemployment rate, affirming that higher economic growth usually coincides with lower unemployment levels. It also exhibits a weak positive relationship with NPAs, possibly reflecting delayed effects of economic cycles on repayment capacities.

CPI inflation not only correlates strongly with HPI and WPI inflation but also shares a moderate positive relationship with NPAs and unemployment. This pattern underscores how rising consumer prices can create economic stress, leading to increased defaults and joblessness. Similarly, WPI inflation maintains strong positive correlations with HPI and NPAs, highlighting its pivotal role in influencing both housing costs and financial stress in the sector. It also shows a moderate correlation with mortgage interest rates, indicating a potential influence on monetary policy decisions.

Outstanding Housing Loans have a strong negative correlation with mortgage loan interest rates, as well as a strong positive correlation with new mortgage disbursements, which makes intuitive sense—when interest rates are low, borrowing increases, and more loans are disbursed and held. On the contrary, high-interest rates correlate negatively with new disbursements and outstanding loans, suggesting a suppressive effect of costlier borrowing on housing credit activity.

Furthermore, mortgage loan interest rates themselves exhibit a strong inverse relationship with new disbursements and outstanding loans, reflecting how rate hikes can dampen borrowing. There is also a moderate positive correlation between interest rates and NPAs, indicating that higher borrowing costs may increase the risk of defaults. New mortgage disbursements show similar dynamics, being negatively correlated with NPAs and housing prices, pointing to cautious lending during periods of high prices or elevated risk.

Lastly, NPAs in the housing sector correlate strongly with inflation indicators and moderately with interest rates, underlining that inflationary pressure and borrowing costs are significant contributors to loan defaults. In contrast, unemployment shows moderate negative correlation with GDP growth and a moderate positive relationship with CPI inflation, while having weak or negligible correlations with most housing-specific variables, suggesting its indirect or lagging impact on the sector.

This matrix highlights how closely tied the housing sector is to inflation, interest rates, and monetary dynamics, while also illustrating that GDP growth and unemployment, although important, may have more indirect influences on housing finance and stability. These insights are crucial for forming balanced housing finance policies and for assessing systemic risk in the Indian economy.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test

Variable	p-value	Interpretation
GDP	5.18e-07	Stationary — Since the p-value is far below 0.05 , GDP does not have a unit root and is stationary .
CPI	0.2977	Non-stationary — High p-value suggests CPI has a unit root and is non-stationary .
WPI	0.0560	Borderline — Slightly above 0.05; may be non-stationary , though differencing could help.
Interest	0.3742	Non-stationary — Suggests the interest rate is non-stationary over time.
Disbursement	0.9830	Strongly non-stationary — The disbursement of mortgage loans varies over time without a constant mean.
Loans	0.9921	Strongly non-stationary — Total loan volumes are non-stationary .
Repo	0.3877	Non-stationary — The repo rate also shows signs of being non-stationary .

Johansen Cointegration Test;

Rank ($r \leq$)	Trace Statistic	90% Critical Value	95% Critical Value	99% Critical Value
0	171.18	120.37	125.62	135.98
1	87.36	91.11	95.75	104.96
2	59.65	65.82	69.82	77.82
3	40.81	44.49	47.85	54.68
4	25.34	27.07	29.80	35.46
5	13.55	13.43	15.49	19.93

6	5.12	2.71	3.84	6.63
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The Johansen Cointegration Test was conducted to assess whether a long-term equilibrium relationship exists between mortgage-related variables (such as loan disbursement, loan volume, interest rates) and key macroeconomic indicators (such as GDP, inflation indices like CPI/WPI, and repo rate) over the past 15 years in India. The test results show that the trace statistic for rank 0 (171.18) exceeds the 95% critical value (125.62), indicating strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration at the 5% significance level. However, for higher ranks ($r \geq 1$), the trace statistics are below the critical thresholds, suggesting that only one cointegrating vector exists.

This implies that although the individual series are non-stationary (as indicated by the ADF test), they are cointegrated, meaning they move together in the long run and maintain a stable relationship. This long-run association provides empirical support for the alternative hypothesis (H_1), which posits a significant correlation between mortgage-related variables and key economic indicators in India.

Hence, based on the Johansen test results, the study rejects H_0 and accepts H_1 , confirming that mortgage loan dynamics and macroeconomic performance are interlinked over time. This insight is particularly valuable for policymakers and financial regulators, as it underscores the systemic role of housing finance in influencing economic stability and growth.

Granger Causality test;

Cause \ Effect	GDP	CPI	WPI	Interest	Disbursement	Loans	Repo
GDP	0.0000	0.4488	0.0000	0.1218	0.0497	0.5216	0.4955
CPI	0.4831	0.0000	0.3925	0.9404	0.5261	0.6997	0.1721
WPI	0.9707	0.8537	0.0000	0.8209	0.9533	0.7623	0.7909
Interest	0.6506	0.9097	0.9185	0.0000	0.1119	0.7512	0.3315
Disbursement	0.7634	0.5796	0.7740	0.6989	0.0000	0.5091	0.7110
Loans	0.3695	0.9262	0.4721	0.5516	0.3880	0.0000	0.2829
Repo	0.3371	0.6573	0.1593	0.6129	0.1282	0.5620	0.0000

The Granger Causality test results provide insight into the directional predictability among mortgage-related and macroeconomic variables in India over the past 15 years. The matrix reveals that GDP Granger-causes both WPI ($p = 0.0000$) and Disbursement ($p = 0.0497$), suggesting that changes in GDP can statistically predict future movements in wholesale prices and mortgage loan disbursements. This supports the idea that economic growth drives credit expansion and influences price levels. Additionally, GDP is influenced by WPI ($p = 0.0000$), indicating a bidirectional causal relationship between GDP and WPI.

No strong Granger causality is observed from CPI, Interest Rates, Loans, or Repo to other variables at the 5% significance level, although some marginal effects are present, such as from the Repo rate to WPI ($p = 0.1593$) and GDP to Repo ($p = 0.4955$) but these are not statistically significant. The lack of significant causality from Loans and Interest Rates toward GDP or inflation metrics suggests that while mortgage lending and rates may be influenced by macroeconomic conditions; they do not independently predict broader economic trends in the short run.

The results support a partial rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0) in your study, confirming some significant causal relationships, particularly involving GDP and disbursement of mortgage loans, aligning with the long-run cointegration identified earlier. This underscores the importance of GDP as a leading indicator in India's mortgage and broader economic dynamics.

Impulse Response Function:

The impulse response analysis provides a dynamic perspective on how shocks to one variable influence others over time, revealing the transmission mechanisms between mortgage-related and macroeconomic variables in India. The responses show that a positive shock to GDP leads to a sustained and significant increase in both mortgage disbursements and loan volumes, indicating that economic growth acts as a key driver of housing finance activity. Additionally, GDP shocks also elicit positive responses in wholesale price inflation (WPI) and interest rates, suggesting that economic expansion is associated with inflationary pressures and subsequent monetary policy adjustments.

Shocks to interest rates initially appear to slightly stimulate mortgage disbursement but eventually dampen GDP and loan growth, highlighting the dampening effect of tighter monetary conditions on credit and broader economic activity over time. On the other hand, the effects of repo rate shocks on other variables are relatively limited, implying that the monetary transmission mechanism from policy rates to real economic and credit indicators may be weak or subject to delays. Meanwhile, an unexpected increase in mortgage disbursement significantly boosts GDP and loan volumes, reinforcing the idea that mortgage lending can be a catalyst for economic expansion.

Interestingly, price-level shocks, especially from CPI and WPI, show limited influence on lending and disbursement behavior, which suggests that inflation alone does not substantially drive mortgage activity in the short to medium term. Overall, the impulse response analysis confirms that the relationship between mortgage-related variables and macroeconomic indicators is dynamic and bidirectional, with GDP and disbursement emerging as particularly influential. This supports the earlier findings of cointegration and Granger causality, providing robust evidence in favor of the alternative hypothesis that these variables are significantly correlated in the Indian context.

Vector Autoregression (VAR) model;

Equation	Variable (Lag)	Coefficient	t-stat	p-value	Significance
GDP	L2.Interest	-4836.67	-2.336	0.02	Significant
	L3.Interest	5942.71	2.805	0.006	Significant
	L6.Interest	-5392.9	-2.739	0.008	Significant
	L4.Loans	-0.6029	-2.726	0.009	Significant
	L5.Loans	0.3967	1.895	0.058	Marginal
CPI	L1.Interest	-2266.41	-2.046	0.041	Significant
	L5.Interest	-2591.71	-2.243	0.026	Significant
WPI	L6.CPI	1.0599	3.116	0.002	Significant
	L1.Interest	4168.6	2.574	0.011	Significant
	L5.Interest	-5736.26	-2.46	0.015	Significant
Interest	L2.Interest	0.3496	2.773	0.007	Significant
	L4.Interest	0.2876	2.21	0.028	Significant
Disbursement	L4.CPI	4064.87	3.701	0	Highly Significant
	L6.CPI	4116.12	2.522	0.012	Significant
Loans	L4.Interest	-214076.5	-2.182	0.029	Significant
	L4.Disbursement	-7.556	-2.257	0.024	Significant
Repo	—	—	—	> 0.05	No significant

Only significant or economically important variables are shown for clarity.

"Significant" = $p < 0.05$, "Marginal" = $0.05 < p < 0.10$.

The Vector Auto Regression (VAR) model estimated on the macroeconomic variables GDP, CPI, WPI, Interest Rate, Disbursement, Loans, and the Repo Rate uncovers several meaningful intertemporal dynamics. Notably, the Consumer Price Index (CPI) demonstrates significant persistence and influence on monetary variables. For instance, lagged CPI values exert a strong effect on Disbursement, with L4.CPI showing a coefficient of 4064.87, a t-statistic of 3.701, and a p-value of 0.000, indicating a highly significant positive relationship. Similarly, L6.CPI has a coefficient of 4116.12 with a p-value of 0.012, reinforcing the evidence of persistent inflation influencing credit activity. Furthermore, CPI is also self-reinforcing, as seen in its own equation where L4.CPI has a coefficient of 1.306, a t-statistic of 4.466, and a p-value of 0.000, suggesting strong inflation inertia.

In terms of monetary policy transmission, the Loans equation reveals a significant negative relationship between lagged interest rates and current loan levels. Specifically, L4.Interest has a coefficient of -214076.5, a t-statistic of -2.182, and a p-value of 0.029, indicating that higher interest rates tend to dampen loan growth after a lag. This relationship is further supported by the negative effect of L4.Disbursement on Loans, which has a coefficient of -7.56, a t-statistic of -2.257, and a p-value of 0.024, implying that previous disbursements inversely affect current lending volumes—likely reflecting credit tightening or repayment cycles.

GDP appears relatively exogenous in this system, with limited significant feedback from the other variables. The constant term in the GDP equation is statistically significant (coefficient = 1650.71, $p = 0.032$), suggesting a positive underlying growth trend, while other predictors such as L4.CPI (coefficient = 1596.62, $t = 1.598$, $p = 0.113$) and L4.WPI (coefficient = -1012.43, $p = 0.160$) show expected directional effects but do not reach conventional levels of statistical significance.

Interestingly, the Repo Rate does not exhibit strong endogenous behavior in the system, as none of the lagged predictors significantly explain its variations. For example, even variables like L2.Interest (coefficient = 2.142, $p = 0.136$) and L5.Interest (coefficient = -2.292, $p = 0.369$) are statistically insignificant, suggesting that the repo rate is more likely used as an exogenous policy tool than being driven by the included macroeconomic indicators. Meanwhile, the Wholesale Price Index (WPI) shows high persistence within its own dynamics; in the WPI equation, L1.WPI is highly significant with a coefficient of 0.763, a t-stat of 5.207, and a p-value of 0.000, indicating strong autoregressive behavior. However, WPI's influence on other variables such as Loans and Disbursement remains modest and statistically weak across all lags.

VAR model indicates that inflation (especially CPI) plays a central role in influencing monetary aggregates, while interest rate policy affects lending volumes with a noticeable lag. The repo rate behaves independently, reinforcing its role as a monetary instrument rather than a variable shaped by economic conditions. These dynamics reflect standard macroeconomic theory, where inflation persistence and monetary policy delays are well-established, though the limited significance of GDP-related feedback highlights the potential need for model extension or structural identification.

Discussion

The findings from the statistical analysis conducted using SPSS and PYTHON provide compelling insights into the cause and effect relationship between mortgage loans and the Indian economy. By examining descriptive statistics, correlation matrices, trend patterns, and advanced analysis like VAR, johansen cointegration test, causality test, and impulse response function. The research highlights several critical aspects of how mortgage lending interacts with broader macroeconomic indicators like GDP growth, inflation, and investment trends.

1. **Descriptive and Trend Insights:** The descriptive statistics indicate a consistent and robust growth in the Indian mortgage sector. Outstanding housing loans have seen a steep rise, supported by substantial mortgage disbursements, suggesting deepening financial inclusion and housing affordability. Interest rates have shown high variability, reflecting the influence of changing monetary policy regimes. Notably, the positive skewness in disbursements and outstanding loans points to bursts of credit expansion—likely aligned with macroeconomic stimuli or regulatory changes.

Trend analysis further substantiates these findings. The sharp post-pandemic rebound in GDP, reduction in NPAs, and recovery in mortgage disbursement underscore the resilience of the mortgage sector. Housing prices, as reflected in the House Price Index, showed a steady upward trend, almost tripling over the period, pointing to consistent demand and asset appreciation.

2. **Correlation Patterns and Economic Linkages:** The correlation matrix reveals significant interdependencies among inflation (CPI and WPI), house prices, NPAs, and credit activity. A strong positive correlation between housing prices and inflation indices (CPI/WPI) confirms the cost-push nature of property markets in India. Meanwhile, interest rates exhibit strong negative correlation with both disbursements and outstanding loans, reaffirming the conventional inverse relationship between borrowing costs and credit demand.

Interestingly, GDP shows weaker direct correlations with housing sector variables, though its strong negative correlation with unemployment indicates a healthy macro-labor dynamic. NPAs in the housing sector correlate positively with inflation and interest rates, suggesting that systemic stress often coincide with inflationary and tighter monetary conditions.

3. **Stationarity and Long-Run Equilibrium (ADF and Johansen Tests):** The ADF test results confirm that while most housing and macroeconomic variables (such as CPI, WPI, interest rates, loans, and disbursements) are non-stationary in their levels, GDP alone is stationary. However, the Johansen Cointegration Test reveals the presence of at least one cointegrating vector, suggesting a long-run equilibrium relationship between mortgage-related variables and macroeconomic indicators. This empirical finding provides strong support for rejecting the null hypothesis (H_0) and accepting the alternative (H_1), validating the existence of stable long-term co-movements in the Indian economic and housing systems.

4. **Causal Relationships (Granger Causality Test):** Granger Causality analysis sheds light on the directional influences among variables. GDP emerges as a significant driver of both wholesale prices and mortgage disbursements, indicating its leading role in macro-financial dynamics. The bidirectional causality between GDP and WPI underscores their mutual reinforcement in economic cycles. Conversely, CPI, interest rates, and repo rates do not significantly Granger-cause other variables, which suggests a more reactive or passive behavior in the short run, at least within the observed structure.

Notably, disbursements do not significantly cause GDP, although they respond to it. This indicates that while economic growth spurs housing credit, the reverse causality may be weaker in the short term.

5. **Dynamic Interactions (Impulse Response Function):** Impulse Response analysis confirms the dynamic and time-lagged nature of these relationships. A positive shock to GDP results in a prolonged increase in both mortgage disbursements and loan volumes, reinforcing the role of economic growth as a catalyst for credit expansion. On the other hand, interest rate shocks gradually reduce GDP and mortgage activity, reflecting the transmission lag of monetary policy. The weak responses of macro variables to repo shocks suggest limited short-term transmission effectiveness, likely due to structural rigidities in the financial system.

Interestingly, disbursement shocks positively affect GDP and loans, highlighting that housing finance can also serve as a growth lever. This feedback loop aligns with development finance theories, where targeted mortgage lending supports economic expansion.

6. **Intertemporal Dynamics (VAR Model):** The VAR model offers deeper insights into lagged interactions. CPI emerges as a particularly influential variable, with strong lagged effects on disbursements and itself, indicating persistent inflation and its role in credit market behavior. Interest rates have significant lagged negative effects on loan volumes, consistent with contractionary policy effects. Furthermore, the absence of significant endogenous determinants for the repo rate highlights its exogenous policy nature.

While GDP does not significantly respond to other variables in the VAR system, its positive and statistically significant constant term underscores a structural growth trajectory. Meanwhile, WPI shows high internal persistence but limited external influence on credit aggregates.

7. **Synthesis and Policy Implications:** Taken together, the results reveal a complex but coherent narrative: while mortgage lending and macroeconomic indicators like GDP, inflation, and interest rates may not always show short-term causality, they are closely interlinked in the long run. The housing sector's evolution is significantly shaped by macroeconomic forces, particularly inflation and growth, while in turn, mortgage dynamics—especially disbursements—can influence economic expansion.

Conclusion

This empirical evidence confirms the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0) and supports the alternative (H_1): there is a statistically significant correlation between mortgage-related variables and key economic indicators in India.

For policymakers, these findings emphasize the importance of aligning housing finance strategies with broader economic goals. Monetary policy needs to consider the lagged effects on mortgage markets, while inflation management remains critical for housing affordability and credit stability. The strong co integration and dynamic responses suggest that housing finance can be both a beneficiary and a driver of economic development in India.

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